

Supplemental Information for

The State of Global Catastrophic Risk Research: A Bibliometric Review

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Figure S1: Percentage of documents in each cluster, by publication year. The first ten years in this plot have only very few papers and are therefore quite noisy.

Figure S2: Overall amount of documents per cluster. This includes all papers that mention GCR/ER anywhere in abstract, title or text (if available) and are connected by at least two references with the rest of the literature.

Figure S3: Average number of authors and unique authors per document for all clusters. By the average number of unique authors we mean the total number of unique authors in a cluster divided by the total number of documents in that cluster. If this is much lower than the average number of authors per paper, it reflects a dominance of certain key authors (e.g. in the Global Resilience and Food Security clusters),

Figure S4: Main authors per cluster. We note that this figure, as well as some others in this supplement, still reflect some false positives (i.e. authors of articles which use the terms GCR/ER in their text even though the concepts of GCR/ER as understood in the paper are not that article’s primary focus); this is a limitation of our systematic keyword-based approach (see Section 2 in the main text).

Figure S5: Number of author affiliations per institution for all clusters

Figure S6: Number of author affiliations per institution for the clusters

Figure S7: Number of author affiliations per country across all clusters.

Figure S8: Number of country author affiliations for the clusters

Figure S9: Main publication outlets by cluster

Figure S10: Main keywords by cluster